

NEW EXAMPLES OF DIVISIBILITY SEQUENCES

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Abstract

We show that if a full group of invertible matrices is embedded in an affine space, then the determinant divisibility sequence associated with the set of endomorphisms given by taking n th powers of matrices is a product of Lucas sequences.

1. Introduction

By a *divisibility sequence* we shall mean a sequence $\{d_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ of integers such that if $n|m$, then $d_n | d_m$. One of the most famous divisibility sequences is the Fibonacci sequence: 0, 1, 1, 2, 3, 5, 8, 13, 21, 34, ... which arises from the linear recurrence $F_n = F_{n-1} + F_{n-2}$. This is an example of the Lucas sequences: $L_n = \frac{\alpha^n - \beta^n}{\alpha - \beta}$, where α, β are the roots of a quadratic polynomial over \mathbb{Z} . See [1] for a complete classification of linear recurrence divisibility sequences and [4], [5], [6] for an introduction to other divisibility sequences. In this paper we discuss properties of certain matrix divisibility sequences. We follow the approach initiated in [3].

2. Matrix Divisibility Sequence

Let S be a commutative ring with 1. Let $M_r(S)$ be the ring of $r \times r$ matrices with entries in S . By the divisor class of a matrix $M \in M_r(S)$ we mean the coset $GL_r(S) \cdot M$ of M with respect to the natural left action of $GL_r(S)$. We say that a matrix $M \in M_r(S)$ divides a matrix $N \in M_r(S)$ if there exists a matrix $Q \in M_r(S)$ such that $N = QM$. If M divides N , then any element of the divisor class of M also divides N . Let (Γ, \cdot) denote a semigroup. A *divisibility sequence of matrices* over a commutative ring S , indexed by Γ , is a collection of matrices $\{M_\alpha\}_{\alpha \in \Gamma}$ in $M_r(S)$, such that if α divides β in Γ , then M_α divides M_β in $M_r(S)$. If $\{M_\alpha\}_{\alpha \in \Gamma}$ is a divisibility sequence of matrices, then by the multiplicativity of the determinant

$\{det(M_\alpha)\}_{\alpha \in \Gamma}$ is a divisibility sequence of elements of the ring S .

We fix a faithful representation:

$$[\cdot] : \Gamma \hookrightarrow \text{End}(\mathbb{A}_S^r) : \alpha \mapsto [\alpha]$$

of Γ into the group of endomorphisms of the affine r -dimensional space \mathbb{A}_S^r over S .

Definition 1. Let $x \in \mathbb{A}_S^r$. The *matrix divisibility sequence* associated with $(\Gamma, [\cdot])$ is the sequence of Jacobians $\{J_\alpha(x)\}_{\alpha \in \Gamma}$ which are $r \times r$ matrices with (i, j) -entry given by partial differentials:

$$[J_\alpha(x)]_{i,j} := \partial(([\alpha](x))_i) / \partial x_j,$$

where $([\alpha](x))_i$ is the i th entry of the value of the endomorphism $[\alpha]$ on x . The associated *determinant divisibility sequence* is defined by $\{det(J_\alpha(x))\}_{\alpha \in \Gamma}$.

3. Main Result

From now on we fix $\Gamma = \mathbb{N}$. Consider the group G of all invertible $r \times r$ matrices with the embedding:

$$G \rightarrow \mathbb{A}^{r^2} : \begin{bmatrix} X_{11} & \cdots & X_{1s} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ X_{s1} & \cdots & X_{rr} \end{bmatrix} \mapsto (X_{11}, \dots, X_{1r}, \dots, X_{r1}, \dots, X_{rr})$$

We define the endomorphism $[n]$ for $n \in \mathbb{N}$. Let $X := [X_{ij}] \in G$ and respectively $X^n := [\bar{X}_{kl}] \in G$, where we treat \bar{X}_{kl} as functions of X_{ij} , for $1 \leq i, j, k, l \leq r$. We define $[n] : \mathbb{A}^{r^2} \rightarrow \mathbb{A}^{r^2}$ as

$$[n](X_{11}, \dots, X_{1r}, \dots, X_{r1}, \dots, X_{rr}) = (\bar{X}_{11}, \dots, \bar{X}_{1r}, \dots, \bar{X}_{r1}, \dots, \bar{X}_{rr}).$$

Then, the Jacobian J_n of the n th power of the matrix X has the form:

$$J_n = \frac{d(X^n)}{dX} \quad D_n = \det J_n.$$

Theorem 2. Let $X \in GL_r(\mathbb{Z})$ and $\lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_r$ be the eigenvalues of X . Then for every $n \geq 1$:

$$D_n = \prod_{1 \leq i, j \leq r} (\lambda_j^{n-1} + \lambda_i \lambda_j^{n-2} + \lambda_i^2 \lambda_j^{n-3} + \dots + \lambda_i^{n-2} \lambda_j + \lambda_i^{n-1}) \tag{1}$$

is an integer and the sequence $\{D_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ is a determinant divisibility sequence.

Proof. Let X, Y, Z be square $r \times r$ matrices. Assume that the entries of matrices Y and Z are functions of the entries of the matrix X . Then, the following matrix derivative formula holds ([2]):

$$\frac{d(YZ)}{dX} = (I \otimes Y) \frac{dZ}{dX} + (Z^t \otimes I) \frac{dY}{dX}, \tag{2}$$

where \otimes denotes the Kronecker product, I is the identity matrix of rank r , and A^t denotes the transpose matrix of A . In addition we will use the following property of the Kronecker product:

$$(A \otimes C)(B \otimes D) = AB \otimes CD \tag{3}$$

for any square matrices A, B, C, D of the size $r \times r$.

Using (2) we compute the Jacobians of the n th power of the matrix X

$$J_n = \frac{d(X^n)}{dX} = \frac{d(X^{n-1}X)}{dX} = (I \otimes X^{n-1}) \frac{dX}{dX} + (X^t \otimes I) \frac{dX^{n-1}}{dX}.$$

By induction and the property (3) of the Kronecker product we get:

$$J_n = \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} (X^t)^k \otimes X^{n-1-k}.$$

Let $N := J_X$ be the Jordan normal form of $X \in GL_r(\mathbb{Z})$. Then, $X = PNP^{-1}$, for some invertible matrix $P \in GL_r(\mathbb{C})$. Hence,

$$\begin{aligned} J_n &= \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} ((PNP^{-1})^t)^k \otimes (PNP^{-1})^{n-1-k} = \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} (P^{-1})^t (N^t)^k (P)^t \otimes P N^{n-1-k} P^{-1} = \\ &= ((P^{-1})^t \otimes P) \left[\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} ((N^t)^k \otimes N^{n-1-k}) \right] (P^t \otimes P^{-1}) \end{aligned}$$

and the determinant divisibility sequence is of the form:

$$D_n = \det J_n = \det \left[\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} ((N^t)^k \otimes N^{n-1-k}) \right].$$

The matrix $(N^t)^k$ is a lower triangular matrix whose diagonal consists of the eigenvalue powers λ_i^k . Hence, the Kronecker product $(N^t)^k \otimes N^{n-1-k}$ is a lower triangular block matrix whose blocks are upper triangular matrices with diagonals composed of terms $\lambda_i^k \lambda_j^{n-1-k}$. Therefore we can conclude that:

$$D_n = \prod_{1 \leq i, j \leq r} (\lambda_j^{n-1} + \lambda_i \lambda_j^{n-2} + \lambda_i^2 \lambda_j^{n-3} + \dots + \lambda_i^{n-2} \lambda_j + \lambda_i^{n-1}).$$

The right hand side is the product of the values of symmetric polynomials computed at eigenvalues of the matrix X . The Galois group of the splitting field of the characteristic polynomial of X acts trivially on these algebraic integers, hence $D_n \in \mathbb{Z}$. For any $n, m \in \mathbb{N}$ such that n divides m we have $n\lambda_i^{(n-1)} | m\lambda_i^{(m-1)}$ (for $\lambda_j = \lambda_i$) and $(\lambda_i^n - \lambda_j^n) | (\lambda_i^m - \lambda_j^m)$ (for $\lambda_j \neq \lambda_i$). Therefore, the sequence D_n is a divisibility sequence. \square

Remark 3. If the matrix X has distinct eigenvalues then the integer D_n can be simplified to the form:

$$D_n = n^r [\det X]^{n-1} \prod_{1 \leq i \neq j \leq r} \left(\frac{\lambda_i^n - \lambda_j^n}{\lambda_i - \lambda_j} \right)^2.$$

4. Examples

1) Let $X \in \text{GL}_2(\mathbb{Z})$ and $a = \text{tr}X, b = \text{tr}^2X - 4\det X$. Then, using Theorem 2 we obtain the sequence presented in [3], Example 4.3:

$$D_n = \frac{n^2}{b} [\det X]^{n-1} \left(\left(\frac{a + \sqrt{b}}{2} \right)^n - \left(\frac{a - \sqrt{b}}{2} \right)^n \right)^2.$$

2) Let $X \in \text{GL}_3(\mathbb{Z})$ and $b = -\text{tr}X, c = X_{11} + X_{22} + X_{33}, d = -\det X$. The discriminant of the characteristic polynomial of X is $\Delta = (4\Delta_0^3 - \Delta_1^2)/27$, where $\Delta_0 = b^2 - 3c$ and $\Delta_1 = 2b^3 - 9bc + 27d$. We obtain the divisibility sequence defined by:

$$D_n = \frac{n^3(-d)^{n-1}}{\Delta} \prod_{i=1}^3 \left[\left(\frac{b + \epsilon^i A + \epsilon^{2i} \bar{A}}{3} \right)^n - \left(\frac{b + \epsilon^{i+1} A + \epsilon^{2i+2} \bar{A}}{3} \right)^n \right]^2,$$

where $A = \sqrt[3]{(\Delta_1 + \sqrt{-27\Delta})/2}, \bar{A} = \sqrt[3]{(\Delta_1 - \sqrt{-27\Delta})/2}$ and ϵ is a fixed primitive cube root of unity.

3) It is easy to compute values of D_n for any square matrix X . The matrix $X = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -2 & -6 \\ 0 & 1 & 3 \\ -1 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \in \text{GL}_3(\mathbb{Z})$ gives the following divisibility sequence:

n	D_n	factorization of D_n
1	1	1
2	800	$2^5 5^2$
3	177147	3^{11}
4	12390400	$2^{12} 5^2 11^2$
5	101025125	$5^3 29^2 31^2$
6	40956386400	$2^5 3^{11} 5^2 17^2$
7	17195158625743	$7^3 41^2 43^2 127^2$
8	2097446912000000	$2^{21} 5^6 11^2 23^2$
9	116366997680401329	$3^{20} 5^3 109^2$
10	1865976489302500000	$2^5 5^7 29^2 31^6$
11	42038200804419417851	$11^3 131^2 857^2 1583^2$
12	37991519596669194547200	$2^{12} 3^{11} 5^2 11^2 17^2 71^2 109^2$
13	5207914793773442748752677	$13^3 1637^2 4057^2 7331^2$
14	323985952722322674280901600	$2^5 5^2 7^3 41^2 43^6 83^2 127^2$
15	7972611872817713189931453375	$3^{11} 5^3 29^2 31^2 2969^2 7109^2$
16	347979934553230802944000000	$2^{30} 5^6 11^2 23^2 47^2 383^2$

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References

- [1] J.P. Bezzivin, A. Ptheo, A.J. van der Poorten. A full characterization of divisibility sequences, *Amer. J. Math.* **112** (1990), 985-1001.
- [2] M. Brooks. The Matrix Reference Manual, <http://www.ee.ic.ac.uk/hp/staff/dmb/matrix/intro.html>.
- [3] G. Cornelissen, J. Reynolds. Matrix divisibility sequences, *Acta Arith.* **156** (2012), 177-188.
- [4] P. Ingram. Elliptic divisibility sequences over certain curves, *J. Number Theory* **123** (2007), no. 2, 473-486.
- [5] Rachel Shipsey. Elliptic divisibility sequences, Ph.D. thesis, Goldsmiths College, University of London, (2000), <http://homepages.gold.ac.uk/rachel>.
- [6] J. H. Silverman. Generalized greatest common divisors, divisibility sequences, and Vojta's conjecture for blowups, *Monatsh. Math.*, **145** (2005), 333-350.